

Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of unidirectional interlayer hybrid FRP composites

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on developing hybrid pseudo-ductile FRP composites for externally bonded strengthening of reinforced concrete structures. Three types of dry unidirectional fabrics were used to create two interlayer hybrid composites via hand lay-up: (i) glass with ultra-high modulus carbon and (ii) high strength carbon with ultra-high modulus carbon. The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IIc}) of the composites interface was measured through tensile testing on specimens with a single cut in the central carbon layer. It was confirmed that catastrophic delamination can be prevented if the mode II energy release rate (G_{II}) at the first fracture is lower than (G_{IIc}). Both hybrid composites exhibited pseudo-ductile behavior with carbon layer fragmentation and dispersed delamination.

KEYWORDS

Hybrid composite; mode II interlaminar fracture toughness; fragmentation; pseudo-ductility.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are known for their lack of ductility, often experiencing sudden and catastrophic failure without warning. They are fragile and therefore unable to provide a warning prior to failure. This means that high safety factors must be applied, leading to oversized and therefore less economical solutions. Moreover, FRP is generally not strongly recommended for structures requiring high ductility, such as those in seismic zones.

A new generation of hybrid pseudo-ductile FRP composites has emerged in recent years. These materials maintain their integrity even after reaching their "yield" stress and exhibit a tensile stress-strain curve resembling metal-like ductile failure. Pseudo-ductile composites are characterized by a tensile stress-strain curve with a flat-topped branch. This allows for greater safety margins in composite structure design.

Hybrid pseudo-ductile composites are composed of two types of fibre reinforcements with different failure strains, e.g., carbon and glass fibres, embedded in a common matrix system. Pseudo-ductility results from the fragmentation of the low strain (LS) material and stable delamination between the LS and the undamaged high strain (HS) material. Even so, achieving non-catastrophic behaviour is possible with some configurations of hybrid composites by selecting the appropriate absolute thickness of the LS material layer, relative thickness (i.e., proportion of layer thicknesses), stiffness, stacking sequence, and strength of the involved reinforcing materials.

Key requirements for pseudo-ductility are (i) high mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IIc}) of the layer interfaces and (ii) low strain energy release rate at the first fracture (Jalalvand et al., 2015b). Czél and Wisnom (Czél & Wisnom, 2013) demonstrated that maintaining mode II energy release rate (G_{II}) below G_{IIc} prevents catastrophic delamination in hybrid composites.

Currently, there is a considerable body of research on hybrid pseudo-ductile composites produced using thin-ply prepregs (Czél et al., 2016; Czél & Wisnom, 2013; Fotouhi et al., 2016; Jalalvand et al., 2014, 2015a, 2015b; Marino & Czél, 2021; Mesquita et al., 2022; Swolfs et al., 2015; Wisnom et al.,

2016). These materials are commonly utilized in the aerospace industry due to their ability to meet high standards of quality and performance. However, the cost of prepregs and their manufacturing process can be expensive. Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the performance of hybrid pseudo-ductile composites made from alternative, more cost-effective materials and manufacturing processes, particularly for applications in industries like construction, which require large quantities of materials.

Ribeiro *et al.* (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2018a, 2018b, 2019; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2021) have extensively explored the pseudo-ductility of hybrid composites for strengthening concrete structures. Their work encompasses the development of hybrid pseudo-ductile composites, their characterization under quasi-static, low-cycle, and fatigue loading, their application to concrete columns under quasi-static loading, as well as analytical and numerical modeling. The hybrid pseudo-ductile composites were manufactured using common and cost-effective processes such as hand lay-up, successfully avoiding abrupt failure and improving the efficiency of the LS material. However, in this set of studies, G_{IIc} was always estimated and never experimentally measured.

In the present work, G_{IIc} of glass/carbon and carbon/carbon interface was measured in hybrid specimens under tensile loading. The laminate architecture introduced by Wisnom (Wisnom, 1992) and Cui *et al.* (Cui *et al.*, 1994) was employed, featuring a symmetrical layup with a pre-cut unidirectional LS layer sandwiched between continuous HS layers. This architecture introduces a discontinuity in the central layer, perpendicular to the fiber orientation, to induce shear stresses between the layers. In such tests, the measured energy release rate represents pure mode II conditions. Typical commercial raw materials (dry fibres and epoxy resin) typically adopted in civil engineering applications were used to produce the hybrid composites.

TENSILE CHARACTERIZATION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL INTERLAYER HYBRID COMPOSITES

This section provides an overview of the tensile behavior of unidirectional hybrid pseudo-ductile composites. It includes information regarding their damage modes, mode II energy release rate, and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness.

Damage modes

Unidirectional hybrid composites subjected to uniaxial tension always exhibit an initial damage mode characterized by the failure of the LS material. However, the subsequent damage modes depend on the properties and configuration of the composite reinforcing materials (Jalalvand *et al.*, 2015b). After LS material failure, four different damage modes may occur (Jalalvand *et al.*, 2015a) (see Figure 1): (i) premature HS material failure, (ii) unstable delamination, (iii) LS material fragmentation, and (iv) LS material fragmentation and stable delamination.

Figure 1: Damage mode of longitudinal section: (a) premature HS failure; (b) unstable delamination; (c) LS layer fragmentation; (d) LS fragmentation and stable delamination

Except for cases of premature HS material failure, hybrid composites undergo a multi-stage damage process. Figure 2 schematically illustrates typical tensile stress-strain curves. These curves exhibit an initial linear stage followed by a transition stage, during which the damage process of the LS material can lead to sudden delamination or progressive fragmentation, depending on the energy released during the damage process.

Figure 2: Illustration of nonlinear quasi-static tensile pseudo-ductile behaviour and definition of 'yield' stress and pseudo-ductile strain

The 'yield' stress is defined as the stress at which the response deviates from the initial linear elastic line, which is close to the stress at which the LS material starts to fail ($\sigma@LF$). In the present work, $\sigma@LF$ and the corresponding failure strain of LS material are assumed as the first load drop. The pseudo-yield strain (ϵ_{pd}) is defined as the extra strain between the final failure strain and the strain on the extrapolated initial slope line at the failure stress of the stress-strain diagram.

Mode II energy release rate

As explained in Czél *et al.* (Czél & Wisnom, 2013), stable pull out of LS material is only possible if, after the first fracture, the laminate can sustain the applied load. To achieve this, G_{II} should be lower than G_{IIC} . An approximate estimation of G_{II} can be obtained using the following equation (Czél *et al.*, 2016; Czél *et al.*, 2017; Czél, Rev, *et al.*, 2018; Jalalvand *et al.*, 2015b):

$$G_{II} = \frac{\epsilon_{LS}^2 \cdot E_{LS} \cdot t_{LS} (2 \cdot E_{HS} \cdot t_{HS} / 2 + E_{LS} \cdot t_{LS})}{8 \cdot E_{HS} \cdot t_{HS} / 2} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where ϵ_{LS} is the failure strain of LS material, E is the elastic modulus and t is the nominal cured layer thickness, while the subscripts LS and HS refer to the low strain and high strain layers. Nominal cured layer thickness of LS material, t_{LS} , is the sum of LS dry fabric thickness, t_{LS_f} , and the resin thickness of LS material, t_{LS_m} :

$$t_{LS} = t_{LS_f} + t_{LS_m} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Nominal cured layer thickness of HS material, t_{HS} , is the sum of HS dry fabric thickness, t_{HS_f} , and the resin thickness of HS material, t_{HS_m} :

$$t_{HS} = t_{HS_f} + t_{HS_m} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Since resin thickness of LS and HS materials cannot be deterministically measured in hybrid composites fabricated using liquid resin, it is assumed that resin thickness is proportional to fibre content of each reinforcing material:

$$t_{LS_m} = t_{total} \cdot \frac{t_{LS_f}}{t_{LS_f} + t_{HS_f}} - t_{LS_f} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$t_{HS_m} = t_{total} \cdot \frac{t_{HS_f}}{t_{LS_f} + t_{HS_f}} - t_{HS_f} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where t_{total} is the total thickness of hybrid composite.

To compute E_{LS} and E_{HS} , it was assumed that stiffness could be compute applying a simple linear rule of mixtures:

$$E_{LS} = \frac{t_{LS_f}}{t_{LS_f} + t_{LS_m}} \cdot E_{LS_f} + \frac{t_{LS_m}}{t_{LS_f} + t_{LS_m}} \cdot E_m \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$E_{HS} = \frac{t_{HS_f}}{t_{HS_f} + t_{HS_m}} \cdot E_{HS_f} + \frac{t_{HS_m}}{t_{HS_f} + t_{HS_m}} \cdot E_m \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where E_{LS_f} and E_{HS_f} are the elastic modulus of the LS and HS dry fabric, respectively, and E_m is the elastic modulus of the matrix.

Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness

The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the hybrid pseudo-ductile composite has been determined experimentally in several research works (Czél et al., 2014; Czél, Mészáros, et al., 2018; Marino et al., 2020). Tests were conducted on specimens similar to those proposed by Wisnom (Wisnom, 1992) and Cui *et al.* (Cui et al., 1994), which involved unidirectional composite laminates with central cut plies subjected to tensile loading (Figure 3). This laminate architecture facilitates early initiation and study of delamination, induces shear loads at the interfaces between the discontinuous and continuous layers (promoting pure mode II crack propagation), and allows for straightforward determination of the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness.

Figure 3: Geometry of cut specimens (dimensions in mm)

The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness is calculated using Eq. 8 (Marino et al., 2020):

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{\sigma_{del}^2 \cdot h^2 \cdot E_{LS} \cdot t_{LS}}{8 \cdot E_{HS} \cdot t_{HS} / 2 \cdot (2 \cdot E_{HS} \cdot t_{HS} / 2 + E_{LS} \cdot t_{LS})} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where σ_{del} is the delamination stress and h the full thickness of the laminate ($h = t_{HS} + t_{LS}$). In the present work, σ_{del} is defined as the local maximum stress as it represents the maximum load the sample can withstand before the sudden propagation of delamination, assuming that the stress drop occurs entirely due to the unstable delamination growth.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Materials and test combination

Three different dry unidirectional fabrics were used: (i) ultra-high modulus carbon (S&P C-Sheet 640) (S&P, 2018b), (ii) high strength carbon (S&P C-Sheet 240) (S&P, 2018a), and (iii) E-glass (S&P G-sheet E 90/10) (S&P, 2015). For the sake of simplicity, the fabrics ‘S&P C-Sheet 640’, ‘S&P C-Sheet

240' and 'S&P G-sheet E 90/10' were named as 'CHM', 'CHS' and 'G', respectively. A solvent-free, transparent 2-component epoxy resin with a formulated amine hardener (S&P Resin Epoxy 55 HP) (S&P, 2018c) was used for impregnating the fabrics. These materials are typically used in civil engineering applications.

The density, areal mass, and the fabric fibre layer thickness (ratio between areal mass density and volumetric mass density) are presented in Table 1. Tensile properties of the epoxy resin has been assessed in (Namourah, 2019), by performing tensile tests following ISO 527-2 (ISO, 2012).

Table 1: Properties of raw materials (dry fabrics and epoxy resin)

Material ID	Density [g/cm ³]	Areal mass [g/m ²]	Fibre layer thickness [mm/layer]	Elastic modulus [GPa]	Failure strain [%]
E-glass (G)	2.60	400	0.154	73	2.31
High strength carbon (CHS)	1.79	400	0.225	240	0.98
Ultra high modulus carbon (CHM)	2.10	400	0.189	640	0.33
Epoxy resin	1.15	--	--	3.2	--

Notes: (i) Properties of dry fabrics are based on manufacture's data; (ii) Elastic modulus of epoxy resin was accessed according ISO 527-2 (ISO, 2012); (iii) failure strain was accessed experimentally in a previous work of the authors (Ribeiro et al., 2021)

Two hybrid laminates were studied: (i) one combining glass (G) and ultra-high modulus carbon (CHM) fibers, and (ii) one combining high-strength (CHS) and ultra-high modulus carbon (CHM) fibers. In the glass/carbon composites, four layers of G were used in the outer plies, while one layer of CHM was applied at the center ply. In the carbon/carbon composites, two layers of CHS were used in the outer plies, and one layer of CHM was applied at the center ply. These specific combinations were chosen based on the authors' expertise (see (Ribeiro et al., 2018a, 2018b; Ribeiro et al., 2020)) to maximize the pseudo-ductile behavior of the resulting configurations, aiming for the combination with the highest 'yield' stress or pseudo-ductile strain. Two types of specimen were produced using both combinations: (i) pristine specimens (i.e. not cut) and (ii) cut-ply specimens with central cut plies.

Specimen manufacturing

Prior to the manufacturing, dry fabrics were cut into rectangular pieces (300 mm × 300 mm) to produce composite laminates with the desired fibre architectures (see Figure 4 (a)). In the case of cut-ply specimens, a precision knife was utilized to create a central cut in CHM dry fabric perpendicular to the fibre direction before the lamination (see Figure 4 (b)).

The lamination was done in a preparation room with temperature of 21 °C ± 3 °C and relative humidity of 50 % ± 10 %. The epoxy resin was prepared mixing its two components and then used to impregnate by hand lay-up impregnation (see Figure 4 (c)). The following fabrication protocol was adopted:

- i. saturation of the first fabric layer with epoxy resin (both sides with hand lay-up) and placement on a flat base, adjusting it manually;
- ii. application of pressure with a wood roller to remove both the excess of epoxy resin and the remaining air bubbles;
- iii. repeat the previous steps for subsequent layers positioned according to the lamination plan to produce the desired laminates;

- iv. after positioning of all layers, final application of pressure by the same wood roller to remove the excess of resin and air bubbles.

All laminates were demoulded after 7 days of curing. After that, post-curing process was applied on the manufactured specimens for 24 hours at 60 °C (see Figure 4 (d)).

Figure 4: Specimen's manufacturing and testing: (a) cut dry fabrics, (b) detail of central cut in CHM fabric, (c) hand lay-up process, (d) post-curing in electric muffle kiln, and (e) test set-up

Specimen geometry and test setup

Six rectangular hybrid composite specimens were extracted (cut) from each laminate produced, composing each series. The geometry of the hybrid composite specimens were 260/160/20 [mm] (length/free length/width). The actual cross sectional area dimensions of each specimen were measured by taking three values of thickness along the specimen free length prior to testing. Table 2 presents the configuration, layer thickness, and total thickness of the hybrid composite specimens. Aluminium tabs of 50.0 × 20.0 × 1.6 [mm] were glued with cyanoacrylate glue at each end of the specimen to minimize gripping effects.

Table 2: Studied combinations

Material combination	LS layer thickness [mm]	HS layer thickness [mm]*	Total thickness [mm] (COV [%])**
2G/1CHM/2G Cut	0.190*	0.616	2.79 (3.07)
2G/1CHM/2G	0.190*	0.616	2.45 (3.68)
1CHS/1CHM/1CHS Cut	0.190*	0.450	2.02 (2.98)
1CHS/1CHM/1CHS	0.190*	0.450	2.30 (5.68)

Notes: *based on manufacture's data; **measured of total thickness (fibers + matrix) with a digital calliper; COV is the coefficient of variation of the corresponding series.

Volumetric fraction of the studied combinations, based on the fibre areal mass of the reinforcing materials, according the manufacturer, and the total thickness of the hybrid composites is given in Table 3. Mean fibre volume fraction of composites manufactured by hand lay-up was ca. 29%. The void analysis was not performed in the scope of this work.

Table 3: Volumetric fraction of studied combinations.

Material combination	LS material [%]	HS material [%]	Matrix [%]
2G/1CHM/2G Cut	6.77	22.08	71.15
2G/1CHM/2G	7.75	25.12	67.13
1CHS/1CHM/1CHS Cut	9.36	22.28	68.37
1CHS/1CHM/1CHS	8.22	19.57	72.22

Tensile tests were carried out at room temperature on a universal testing machine (MTS Exceed E45.104), equipped with a 100 kN load cell (with a linear error less than 0.05% of the full scale). The

specimens were held between the grips of the testing machine and extended (at a rate of 1 mm/min) up to failure. Strains were measured with a video extensometer system – Model XT-104 (typical extension resolution of 0.6 μm and accuracy class B-2) – (see Figure 4 (d)). Post processing of the results was performed by means of the commercial software GOM correlate to obtain a full field surface strain measurement. The elastic modulus, according to ISO 527–5 (ISO, 2009), was defined as the slope of stress–strain curve for the strains 0.0005 and 0.0025.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 illustrates the stress-strain curves for the examined specimen configurations: (i) pristine (uncut) and (ii) cut-ply specimens. Outlier results were disregarded. Both configurations exhibited a very similar pseudo-ductile response with multiple fractures. This indicates that unstable delamination was avoided even in the cut specimens. The tensile load-strain curves for these composites display an initial linear behavior, followed by a slightly rising plateau (more noticeable in 2G/1CHM/2G than 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS composites), and a second rising almost linear branch. To understand these curves, a further analysis of the damage mode of the composites is next presented.

Figure 5: Pseudo-ductile tensile responses of (a) carbon/carbon and (b) glass/carbon combinations

When comparing the results of pristine specimens for both hybrid composites, it is observed that the 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS combination exhibited the highest elastic modulus, E_{hybrid} , ‘yield’ stress, $\sigma_{@LF}$, and strength, σ_u . On the other hand, the 2G/1CHM/2G combination achieved the highest values for failure strain of the LS material, ϵ_{LS} , and strain at failure, ϵ_u , were achieved by the 2G/1CHM/2G combination. The mean values of the tensile properties and their coefficient of variation (COV) are presented in Table 4 for each series.

Table 4: Results of tensile tests

Combinations	$\sigma_{@LF}$	σ_u	ϵ_{LS}	ϵ_u	E_{hybrid}
	[MPa] (COV [%])	[MPa] (COV [%])	[%] (COV [%])	[%] (COV [%])	[GPa] (COV [%])
2G/1CHM/2G cut	256.80* (5.78)	436.23 (3.97)	0.44* (6.66)	2.30 (4.74)	62.22 (6.41)
2G/1CHM/2G	282.16 (7.84)	477.99 (8.67)	0.40 (6.69)	2.53 (9.30)	68.76 (4.37)
1CHS/1CHM/1CHS cut	458.90* (4.44)	932.67 (8.67)	0.37* (8.46)	1.28 (3.08)	130.67 (5.81)
1CHS/1CHM/1CHS	408.94 (10.03)	774.75 (10.17)	0.35 (13.81)	1.17 (5.63)	121.52 (5.89)

*in the present work the σ_{del} is defined as the local maximum stress as it represents the maximum load the sample can withstand before the propagation of delamination

Upon reviewing Table 4, it can be concluded that the results show a small variation among them. The COV ranged from 3.97% to 9.30%, for the analyzed properties of 2G/1CHM/2G combination, and from 3.08% to 13.81% for the analyzed properties of the 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS combination.

For the 2G/1CHM/2G pristine combination, the mean value of E_{hybrid} was 68.76 GPa (COV = 4.37%), while for 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS pristine combination, it was equal to 121.52 GPa (COV = 5.89%).

In the case of 2G/1CHM/2G pristine combination, a mean $\sigma_{@LF}$ of 282.16 MPa was registered. For the 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS pristine combination, a mean ‘yield’ stress of 408.94 MPa was registered. The CHM ply started to fragment when the strain reached ca. 0.4%. The strain at the failure of LS fibers (first crack) is identical in both combinations.

Figure 6 illustrates the consecutive phases of the tensile test conducted on cut specimens of 2G/1CHM/2G configuration. The longitudinal strains were measured using a 2D digital image correlation system, allowing for the observation of surface strain fields during the test. The colored scale corresponds to the measured strains. As anticipated, delamination initiates at the center of the specimen, as indicated by high values of longitudinal strain, in the vicinity of the cut (Figure 6 (b)). Subsequently, additional CHM cracks emerge, followed by stable delamination between layers in a sequential manner (Figure 6 (c)-(f)). Delamination regions manifest along the gauge length in a distributed fashion, forming a striped pattern. These delamination areas continue to propagate stably during loading until they are nearly connected (Figure 6 (g)). Eventually, the final failure occurs within the HS layers (Figure 6 (h)). The same damage mode was observed in cut specimens of 1CHS/1CHM/1CHM configuration.

Figure 6: Damage progress of cut 2G/1CHM/2G specimens.

In the case of pristine specimens, the damage mode was mostly similar. However, it is worth noting that the first crack did not appear exactly in the center of the specimen.

Finally, the value of G_{II} as defined in Eq. 1 was computed. The computed G_{II} values were 1.15 N/mm and 0.79 N/mm for the 2G/1CHM/2G and 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS configurations, respectively. These computed G_{II} values are present in Table 5.

The critical value of G_{IIc} was computed according to Eq. 8. The critical stress for delamination (σ_{del}) was extracted from the curves of the cut samples at the first load drop. The computed values for G_{IIc} were 1.83 N/mm for the 2G/1CHM/2G and 1.30 N/mm for the 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS configurations. These values closely align with the ones previously estimated by the authors using analytical modeling (1.46 N/mm for the 2G/1CHM/2G and 1.25 N/mm for the 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS in (Ribeiro et al., 2018a)).

As mentioned earlier, in order to avoid unstable damage modes after the first fracture of the LS material, G_{II} should be lower than the G_{IIc} . Based on this assumption, it can be concluded that unstable damage modes are expected to be avoided in both the 2G/1CHM/2G and 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS composites. Therefore, it can be stated that the calculated values are in very good agreement with the observed damage modes.

Table 5: Strain energy release rate vs. mode II interlaminar fracture toughness.

	G_{II} [N/mm]*	G_{IIc} [N/mm]
2G/1CHM/2G	1.15	1.83
1CHS/1CHM/1CHS	0.79	1.30

* $G_{II} < G_{IIc}$ – stable damage

CONCLUSIONS

This study is a part of the development of new hybrid pseudo-ductile composites for externally bonded strengthening of reinforced concrete structures. The experimental behavior of glass/carbon and carbon/carbon unidirectional interlayer hybrid composites under quasi-static tensile tests is here investigated.

Two types of specimen were produced using both referred to hybrid combinations: (i) pristine specimens (i.e. not cut) and (ii) cut-ply specimens with central cut LS plies. The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IIc}) was assessed using the latter.

For the production of the hybrid composites, conventional commercial raw materials commonly employed in civil engineering applications were chosen. The manufacturing process involved hand lay-up techniques. The mean fibre volume fraction of composites was ca. 29.0%.

The following conclusions can be drawn from this work:

- A stable pseudo-ductile response with multiple fractures was observed in the 2G/1CHM/2G composites and the 1CHS/1CHM/1CHS pristine specimens. As expected, in the pre-cut specimens, delamination initiated at the center of the specimen, near the cut. In these specimens, additional CHM cracks appeared, followed by stable delamination between layers, resulting in stable damage modes characterized by LS fragmentation;
- The G_{II} of the studied pristine specimens was lower than the experimentally determined G_{IIc} . Hence, it can be concluded that the calculated values are in agreement with the observed damage modes because, according to theoretical assumptions, unstable damage modes are avoided when $G_{II} < G_{IIc}$;
- Lastly, the experimentally determined G_{IIc} closely aligns with previous work by the authors, where these values were analytically determined.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.